

DETERMINANTS AND CONSEQUENCES OF STALLED FERTILITY TRANSITION IN NIGERIA

Akinokun Rilwan Akintayo^{1*} and Abdoulie Musa Bah²

¹*Department of Demography and Social Statistics, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria*

²*Department of Mathematics, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria*

**Corresponding Author email: akinokunridwan@gmail.com*

Abstract

Fertility transition, being a shift from high fertility level to low fertility level is central towards the achievement of economic and social development in Nigeria. Studies undertaken in sub-Saharan Africa on fertility transition have identified proximate determinants of fertility such as non-marriage, post-partum amenorrhoea and contraceptive use as some of the key factors inhibiting fertility which may have caused the stall in the fertility transition process in the continent. This paper employed in-depth review of literature as its methodology for assessing the possible determinants leading to the stall in fertility process in Nigeria. The findings show that the major factors contributing to the stall in fertility transition in Nigeria are socio-cultural and religious factors. The paper, therefore, recommends that the Nigerian government needs to scale up programmes towards addressing these socio-cultural and religious factors in order to facilitate fertility transition in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Stalled, Fertility, Transition, Consequences, Determinants, Nigeria*

1.0 Introduction

Fertility transition is the shift from high fertility level to low fertility level. The transition is central towards the achievement of economic and social development in Nigeria. Studies done in sub-Saharan African countries on fertility transition have identified proximate determinants of fertility such as non-marriage, postpartum amenorrhoea and contraceptive use as some of the key factors inhibiting fertility in the continent. The word “stall” refers to an interruption period in an ongoing fertility transition before a country reaches the end of the transition. Fertility transitions are typically driven by declines in marital fertility and this has clearly been the dominant pattern in sub-Saharan African Countries (Babalola *et al.*, 2017). Low levels of socio-economic development, low level of female education, poor access to health services and weak family planning programmes are some of the major factors that have delayed the transition to low fertility rates in Nigeria.

Numonyo *et al.* (2017) assert that Nigerians fertility behaviours must be understood in the context of kinship, parenthood, family and children which are often intertwined with how people survive in a political economy organised around the patriarchal family system, where the husband is the primary breadwinner in most Nigerian cultures. They stress that despite the fact that fertility transition is commonly associated with modernisation processes and development, most Nigerians succumb to the various pressures on fertility reduction due to failed economy, personal hardships and failed development. They primarily succumb to fertility reduction based on these three factors even though having relatively smaller families are very essential for proper child education and adaptation to the society, poverty reduction, reducing hunger in the society,

ensuring sustainability of our cities and communities and reducing the negative effects of climate change, which are some of the sustainable development goals.

The high rate of maternal mortality, infant and child mortality rates in Nigeria has its attendant effect on fertility increase. This is because in the demographic transition, fertility always responds to mortality. Babalola *et al.* (2017) in a study of factors affecting the achievement of fertility intentions in Nigeria, recommend that there is a need for a comprehensive strategy in helping women avoid unwanted pregnancies and government effort needs to be accelerated towards increasing women's knowledge of fertility intentions and strengthening effective ways of contraceptive use. They conclude that there is the need for proper engagement of men on reproductive issues; promote spousal communication, promote smaller family size and efforts towards changing pronatalist attitudes should be incorporated in government strategies.

1.1 Fertility Transition in Nigeria

Olufunmilayo *et al.* (2024), and Feyisetan and Bankole (2009) assert that sustained fertility transition has begun in Nigeria in two separate studies on fertility transition in Nigeria. One of the objectives of the study was to identify some of the factors that have contributed to the decline. They stress that fertility behaviour is conditioned by both social and biological factors and that like other African countries; several factors have contributed to the sustained high fertility levels in Nigeria. These factors include child and infant mortality rate; since fertility is responding to mortality in the demographic transition, early childbearing which has prolonged the range of childbearing extending across almost all of the reproductive life span of female and male. They also identify universal and early marriage, high social values placed on childbearing and low use of contraception as some of the factors responsible for high fertility rate in Nigeria despite the fact that the continent is currently witnessing reduction in fertility. The high rate of fertility in Nigeria despite the consistent decline in fertility in Africa can also be attributed to the momentum of the population in Nigeria.

They stress further that the practice of polygyny in most Nigerian societies has encouraged competition for childbearing among wives thereby sustaining a high fertility rate. They also assert that the use of modern contraception was rejected by most traditional societies with the claim that such practice violates the natural process of procreation and that the traditional long period of breastfeeding and postpartum abstinence is adequate enough for child spacing. They conclude that Nigeria is however witnessing fertility transition due to changes in some of the socio-cultural factors, such as increase in age at marriage, increase in use of modern contraceptives, and improvement in women's education which have gradually eroded the high values placed on childbearing.

Odusina *et al.* (2020) argue that by law of demographic transition, fertility naturally declines in response to falling child mortality; so that if the health and living conditions of the people is improved, there will be reduction in child and infant mortality rate which will invariably lead to fertility reduction thereby actualising the sustainable development goals of poverty reduction, zero hunger, good health and well-being of the people. He suggests erosion of patriarchal family structure which will invariably give more autonomy for the female, promote gender equity and reduce inequality in the society which is Goals 5 and 10 of the sustainable development goals. The attainment of female autonomy, and improved gender equity will also serve as supplements to government efforts towards encouraging the use of modern methods of birth control and family planning.

Abednigo and Ebenezer (2022) posit that despite global fertility decline, Nigeria has been witnessing plague population explosion since independence due to some factors that need to be addressed by individuals and government, most especially on fertility desires. In a similar view, Bongaarts (2008) acknowledged this fact with developing countries that the pace of fertility decline in developing countries was lower around the year 2000 when compared to the mid-1990s and that more than half of the countries in the transition stage in sub-Saharan countries have stalled fertility transition. The answer to this stalled fertility transition can be attributed to economic, political and cultural factors that might have been acting as moderating factors in the cause-effect relationship thereby hindering the fertility measures of the sustainable development goals of two children per woman; thereby having an overall negative effect on the achievement of the sustainable development goals in Nigeria, most especially Goals 1 and 2 of poverty reduction and zero hunger, respectively.

Nigerian culture still places a high premium on childbirth and having large families. Most of the modern family planning techniques such as use of contraceptives are still confronted with strong contempt and rejection on the grounds that they are against the natural process of reproduction. Religious factors on early marriage and polygamous family structure have also exerted more influence on having large families and boosting fertility most especially in the northern part of Nigeria. These are some of the reasons why the northern part of Nigeria is still far behind the achievement of the sustainable development goals when compared to the southern part of the country. For example, girl child education is still very low in northern Nigeria when compared to the southern region. This has in turn triggered gender inequity, increased poverty in the region, poor health care and general well-being of the people, most especially, northern Nigerian women still fair low when compared to the Southern part of the country.

Aondoaseer and Dewua (2020) in a journal on assisted Reproductive Technologies and Fertility Transition in Nigeria asserted that reproductive technologies have helped in bypassing obstacles involved in achieving pregnancy by the conventional methods thereby making it possible for childbirth and pregnancy to occur where otherwise it wouldn't have. This may probably be one of the factors that might have accounted for the stalled fertility transition in Sub-Saharan Africa. They stressed that millions of infertile couples and other similar categories have utilized this improved technology to achieve their fertility desires since 1978 and this has resulted in over 10 million births globally including Nigeria. It has paved the way for more number of live births through test-tube babies which have given rise to alteration of the fertility transition globally even though assisted reproductive technologies are still being confronted with economic, socio-cultural and environmental factors in the society.

They stress further that as long as this factor exists, the influencing effect will persist in terms of affecting the fertility transition in sub-Saharan African countries most especially Nigeria; hence affecting the actualisation of the sustainable development goals. They recommend cultural reorientation and social welfare schemes that will help in addressing the forces that place high value on children thereby forcing couples to have children through artificial reproductive technologies.

1.2 Consequences of Stalled Fertility Transition in Nigeria

Stalled fertility refers to an interruption period in an ongoing fertility transition before a country reaches the end of the transition. There are various factors that might have facilitated stalled fertility in Nigeria such as religious and cultural factors that place a high value on childbearing in the country. Even though fertility transition has been accompanied with decline in Nigeria

including sub-Saharan African countries like Nigeria, there has been some inconsistencies featured with sudden surge or increase in some years making the transition not smooth throughout the years. The figure below depicts the decline in fertility but for some inconsistencies between years 2000 and 2015. The consequence of this inconsistencies which will be referred to “stall” in the fertility transition is that African countries will not be able to reap some of the socio-economic benefits which might have accrued from low fertility and mortality such as increased life expectancy, employment opportunities for the working population and so forth, which have been termed ‘demographic dividends’.

1.3 Determinants of Stalled Fertility Transition in Nigeria

According to Miriam *et al.* (2018) and Stephen *et al.* (2012), early marriage is commonly practiced by women in developing countries, most especially Nigeria. Their articles focus on survival analysis of age at first marriage among women of reproductive age across Nigeria and differences across regions. They assert that age at first marriage may have serious health implications on both the women involved and their children, most especially those under five years old. They justify their study that in Nigeria, few studies have explored age at first marriage and that the current study was designed to fill the gap. It is against this backdrop that it is considered expedient to examine age at first marriage regionally, most especially in northern Nigeria where the scourge is very rampant coupled with religious and cultural doctrines on polygamous family systems in some parts of the country.

Miriam *et al.* (2018) posit that there is need to abolish child marriage in Nigeria due to its attendant consequences and they suggest that in achieving this objective, the constitution of the country needs to be amended to ensure that 18 years is the minimum age for marriage provided in the Child’s Right Act as applicable for customary, civil and religious marriages. They also suggest that there is the need for adequate registration of marriages and births through effective machinery in both rural and urban areas thereby helping the appropriate authorities to enforce the minimum age at marriage throughout the country. They conclude that rural dwellers need to be well enlightened and educated on the health hazards associated with child marriage and stretching the importance and economic benefits of girl child education.

Kingsley and Mudiaga (2020), in a paper on the menace of child marriage in Nigeria and the need for an enabling constitutional provision posit that child marriage remains dominant in Nigeria because early child marriage is accepted within the customary law and tradition of the people despite the various provisions in the Nigerian constitution on the menace. The paper faults the inability of the government in tackling child marriage due to non-enactment of laws regarding this issue by northern states in Nigeria. They conclude that laws and provisions on early marriage within the context of marriage age should be fundamental in addressing the menace of child marriage in Nigeria. Adequate studies have not been conducted in examining the issue of early marriage in Nigeria and this is essential in Nigeria considering the low level of education, self-esteem of women and the religious doctrines attached to early marriage.

Thomas (2010), in a study conducted on socio-cultural factors serving as determinants of divorce rates among women of reproductive age in Nigeria shows a significant relationship between educational background of women of reproductive age and divorce rates involving them. The study also posits a significant relationship between religious affiliations of women and divorce rates. They recommend that social workers, helping professionals and family counsellors need to provide strategies towards solving or reducing divorce by Nigerian couples. Despite the fact that Nigeria with its multi-religious groups and high literacy rate, age of entry into reproduction is still

exacting influence on fertility through divorce rates thereby suggesting intervention study in all parts of the country on age of entry into marriage and reproduction as a factor affecting fertility in Nigeria.

1.4 Family Planning and Fertility Transition in Nigeria

The practice of family planning among couples in terms of contraceptive use and birth spacing among couples in Nigeria still leaves much to be desired most especially in the northern part of the country. This is because of some cultural beliefs on contraceptive use that it is distrusting the natural process of reproduction. Also, some cultures attach more importance to having large families with the belief that they can be of assistance in farm work and can compensate the parents in their old age. Some cultures prefer natural methods of family planning such as postpartum abstinence rather than the use of contraceptive devices with the belief that the use of such modern methods may have its attendant negative effect on the couple most especially the woman.

Some religious beliefs do not support some of the modern methods such as sterilization and would rather throw their weight behind modern methods such as prolonged natural breastfeeding and postpartum abstinence. This explains where fertility levels still remain high in sub-Saharan Africa countries when compared to other regions on the continent. In Demography, family planning is a very important fertility variable that determines parity, birth spacing and even children-ever-born by a particular woman. Several studies have been conducted on contraceptive use as it determines birth spacing and children-ever-born. This paper examines family planning variables as they affect fertility rate across various regions of the country.

Irit *et al.* (2020), in a study on unmet needs for family planning and contraceptive use in Nigeria posit that as at 2017, only one-fifth of all married women of reproductive age in Nigeria experienced unmet needs for contraception which has led to high risky fertility behaviours thereby compromising reproductive rights. They stress further that many women in Nigeria are suffering from lack of empowerment in making contraceptive decisions. They also assert that home barriers, community barriers and lack of health facilities have impeded the extent to which fertility desires can be achieved. They highlight normative, cultural, financial and social factors such as permission of the husband in accessing service providers among others as some of the factors impeding contraceptive and access to family planning services. They conclude that studies can be transformed into programmatic interventions towards improving voluntary use of contraceptives.

Emmanuel *et al.* (2018) and Christine (2006), in a study with a cross-sectional analysis among men in urban Senegal, Kenya and Nigeria, acknowledge that researchers on family planning often overlook the importance of men's involvement in couples' contraception and fertility choices despite the fact that male involvement is a very crucial factor that determines reproductive and sexual health programming. Their study was aimed at assessing whether men's exposure to family planning and demand-generated activities are associated with use of modern contraceptive methods. Their findings reveal city and country variations across geographical contexts and suggest gender-comprehensive and context-specific programmes in reducing unmet needs for family planning.

Odusina *et al.* (2020) and Clara *et al.* (2015), in a study on contextual factors that may influence modern contraceptive use in Nigeria, assert that modern contraceptive use in Nigeria remains low despite socio-economic and health benefits associated with its use. They stress further that given

Nigeria's commitment towards doubling contraceptive prevalence use within four years, there is the need to investigate the mediating factors affecting and mediating use behaviour for various government programmes towards contraceptive use to be responsive and yield positive results. Their study reveals that overall, at the community and individual levels where there is female education, autonomy and access to health care facilities, there is a high percentage of contraceptive use. Their study also reveals that communities with higher proportions of Muslims and polygamous families show negative results in modern contraceptive use.

They submit that in comparison with sub-Saharan African countries, all over the continent except some parts of Nigeria such as southern Nigeria have significantly lower odds of contraceptive use. They assert that place of residence; rural dwellers and poverty had no significant effect on use of modern contraceptives. They conclude that community and individual characteristics were significant factors influencing the use of modern contraceptives in Nigeria and this needs to be taken into consideration in family planning programmes in the country.

Emmanuel *et al.* (2010), in a study on contraceptive practices in Nigeria, acknowledge low rate of contraceptive use despite widespread sexual activity and awareness of various contraceptive methods among Nigerian youths and adolescents. As a result of this, there have been several abortions and unintended pregnancies among youths which has contributed to high maternal mortality rate which indicates large unmet needs for contraceptive use. They stress further that there is research evidence identifying various factors that have contributed to low prevalence of modern contraceptive use in Nigeria with the most prevalent factor being the myths on the side effects of modern contraceptives.

They identify a lack of political will in Nigeria in providing family planning programmes on a larger scale using community programmes and community-oriented approaches in changing the myths about side effects associated with the use of modern contraceptives. Their review highlight concepts and methods in contraception, reasons for low contraceptive practice and use in Nigeria and the need for Nigeria to generate a political priority and will towards making a change in maternal health indicators with the ultimate goal of providing direction in guiding changes in the Nigeria population policy as it affects family planning and contraceptive use.

Emmanuel *et al.* (2018) and Mustapha and Ismaila (2006), in a study on male knowledge, attitude and family planning practices in northern Nigeria, examine linkages between attitudes, socio-economic characteristics and familial contraceptive use. They discover that past family planning programmes in Nigeria were mainly directed towards the women not bearing in mind that it is a joint effort of both men and women. They assert that northern Nigeria remained a patrilineal society which is characterised with early age at marriage of women, that men determine contraceptive and familial fertility decisions. They suggest that willingness of husbands to allow their spouses to adopt and use family planning practices will go a long way in determining the pace of fertility reduction in Nigeria. The results of their study reveal high knowledge of contraceptive use but a generally negative attitude towards limiting family size for economic reasons and consequently low rates of contraceptive use.

They stress further that respondents who showed positive interest towards contraceptive use were more willing to use contraceptives for child spacing than limiting family size. They conclude that the attitudes of men regarding decisions are very important on decisions regarding contraceptive use since knowledge of contraception is already high among respondents who use it and those who don't. As a result, family planning programmes that focused mainly on women will continue

to achieve limited success in northern Nigeria and other patrilineal societies where similar programmes are pursued.

2.0 Methodology

The methodology used for this study was systematic review of scholarly articles based on the objectives of the study. Meanings and definitions of concepts relating population, environment and development were accessed from the Internet, Demography and Health Survey Data sets of African countries. The summary of results and discussions are deduced from the literature.

3.0 Results and Discussions

The findings show that despite the high fertility we are witnessing in Nigeria, Nigeria is still undergoing demographic transition towards fertility reduction. Even though fertility decline is low, Nigeria is still experiencing a transition to lower fertility. Nigerians have faced various economic, political and cultural challenges on fertility reduction even though some of the cultural factors were towards encouraging large family size. Nigeria fertility behaviour must be understood in the context of kinship, parenthood, family and children which are often intertwined with how people survive in a political economy organised around a patriarchal family system; where the husband is the primary breadwinner in most Nigerian cultures.

Findings on fertility transition in Nigeria shows that despite the fact that fertility transition is commonly associated with modernisation processes and development, most Nigerians succumb to the various pressures on fertility reduction due to failed economy, personal hardships and failed development. They primarily succumb to fertility reduction based on these three factors even though having relatively smaller families is very essential for proper child education and adaptation to the society. However, Nigeria is still witnessing fertility transition due to changes in some of the socio-cultural factors such as increase in age at marriage, increase in use of modern contraceptives, and improvement in women's education which have gradually eroded the high values previously placed on childbearing.

Quality education, good health and well-being, and gender equality of the sustainable development goals will go a long way in reducing the high fertility rate we are experiencing in Nigeria through prolonging the age at marriage of women, reducing mortality rate and improving women participation in the labour force. In sub-Saharan Africa where the fertility rate is higher relative to other regions, the attendant consequences and causes are low level of education of the girl child, lack of gender equality, lack of good health conditions and well-being of mothers. These factors have triggered fertility in the region thereby inhibiting the achievement of the sustainable development goals of poverty reduction, zero hunger, and good health conditions and well-being of the people most especially the female population.

4.0 Conclusion

Government of various African countries need to incorporate strategies that will be tailored towards addressing the high fertility rate by expanding access to modern contraceptive methods across the continent and by removing the attitudinal, structural, physical and communication barriers related to policies, systems and norms which have been an obstacle in achieving the policy implications in terms of its objectives. Government of various African countries need to incorporate universal basic education programme of ensuring quality education for the less privileged, ensuring good health and well-being of the sustainable development goals, and

promoting gender equality which will go a long way in reducing the high fertility rate we are experiencing in Nigeria through prolonging the age at marriage of women, reducing mortality rate and improving women participation in the labour force thereby improving the living conditions of the people in general which is the demographic dividend every country is always aspiring for through the demographic transition.

References

- Abednigo Addah, Ebenezer Ikobho, (2022). Demographic and fertility transition in Nigeria: the progress made so far: a literature review. *Babcock University Medical Journal*. 5(2), 110-116.
- Adebowale, Stephen A, Francis A Fagbemigbe, Elijah A Bamgboye, (2011). Contraceptive use: Implication for completed fertility, parity progression and maternal nutritional status in Adegoke, Thomas Gbadebo (2010). Socio-cultural factors as determinants of divorce rates among women of reproductive age in Ibadan metropolis, Nigeria. *Study of tribes and tribals* 8(2), 107-114.
- Aondoaseer Lawrence Kwaghga, RE Dewua, (2020). Assisted Technologies and Fertility Transition in Nigeria. *Benue Journal of Sociology*. Vol.8, No.1, PP 60-79.
- Babalola Stella, Olamide Oyenubi, Mojisola Odeku, (2017). Factors affecting the achievement of fertility intentions in urban Nigeria: analysis of longitudinal data. *BMC Public Health*
- Bamikale J. Feyisetan, Akinrinola Bankole, (2009). Fertility transition in Nigeria: trends and prospects. *asdf*, 461.
- Banjo, Olufunmilayo (2024). Women's empowerment and completed fertility in Nigeria: what is the modulating effect of religion in the relationship? *Women's reproductive health* 11(2), 239-254
- Christine Kessides, (2006). The urban transition in sub-Saharan Nigeria: implications for *environment and development*
- Clara Ladi Ejembi, Tukur Dahiru, Alhaji A Aliyu, (2015). Contextual factors influencing modern contraceptive use in Nigeria. *DHS working papers*.
- Emmanuel A Agege, Ezekiel U Nwose, Stella Odjemogbo, (2018). Parents' perception on factors of early marriage among the Urhobos in Delta State of Nigeria. *International journal of community medicine and public health* 5(2), 411-415.
- Emmanuel Monjok, Andrea Smesny, John E Ekabna, E James Essien, (2010). Contraceptive practices in Nigeria: Literature review and recommendation for future policy decisions. *Open access journal of contraception*
- Irit Sina, Elizabeth Omoluabi, Adenike Jimoh, Kaja Jurczynska, (2020). Unmet needs for family planning and barriers to contraceptive use in Kaduna, Nigeria: Culture, myths and perceptions. *Culture, health & sexuality* 22(11), 1253-1268

*4th African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation Biennial International Conference
Proceedings*

Kingsley O Mrabure, Mudiaga K. Ovakporae, (2020). Unabated menace of child marriage in Nigeria. The need for an enabling constitutional provision. *JL Policy & Globalisation* 98, 179

Miriam Chinyere Anozie, Millicent Ele, Elizabeth Ijeamaka Anika, (2018). The legal, medical and social implications of child marriage in Nigeria. *International journal of law, policy and the family* 32(2), 119-139.

Mustapha C Duze, Ismaila Z Mohammed, (2006). Male knowledge, attitude and family planning practice in northern Nigeria. *Nigerian journal of reproductive health* 10(3), 53-65.

Numonyo Duabo, Dambo, Israel Jeremiah, Akhtar Wally Mahmed, (2017). Determinants of contraceptive use by women in the central senatorial zone of Bayelsa State, Nigeria: A cross-sectional survey.

Oodusina E. K, Titilayo A, Kunnuji M (2020). Fertility Preferences among couples in Nigeria: a Cross sectional study.